

Assessment of Hydrogeomorphic Suitability of Lake Mbemun for Socio-cultural Fishing Festival in the Bachama Chiefdom, Adamawa State, Northeastern Nigeria

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author YE designed the study, performed the Hydrographic and Fluid Mud Surveys as well as the Hydrogeomorphologic analysis of the lake, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author AR wrote on the biological productivity and fishery potentials of the lake. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

The feasibility of socio cultural fishing in any fluvial lake strongly depends on water and fluid mud depths of the lake. In this study, the suitability of Lake Mbemun for a socio cultural fishing festival has been examined. Using the data obtained from hydrographic survey, Bathymetric and fluid mud depth maps of the lake for March 2016 were prepared. Both maps were used for hydro geomorphologic analyses of the lake. Results showed that the lake had a fetch of 2.95 km, a maximum width of 2.01 km and a surface area of 3.65 km², making it widely opened to wind and waves impacts which in turn enhance water mixing and sediment focusing. The lake was also found

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to be generally shallow with a mean depth of 0.81 m, a depth indicator of 1.48 and a relative depth of 0.06%. Its Shoreline Development Index (1.5) indicates its crenulated state which reflects the potentials for development of littoral communities (plants) and high biological productivity. But with fluid mud depths ranging from 0.44 m to 1.26 m in most parts of the lake, it was considered very muddy and unsuitable for a socio-cultural fishing festival. Therefore, Dredging of the lake is recommended for suitable socio-cultural use.

Keywords: Hydrographic survey; bathymetric map; fluid mud map; lake morphometry; socio cultural fishing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lakes are dynamic lentic surface water bodies which constitute integral and vital landscape components in hydro geomorphology; A term used to describe the analysis of hydrographic basins, fluvial processes and the resulting landforms [1]. They are hydro geomorphic features of great interest, considering their significance to humans in terms of vast resource potentials on one hand and their susceptibility to temporal changes in both basin form and water content on the other hand.

Lakes serve as vital sources of water and food supplies to humans as well as important sites for many socio-economic and cultural activities among which are small scale fishing and socio cultural fishing festivals. However, owing to both natural and anthropogenic processes, they are subjected to gradual changes in their basin morphology and loss in hydrological and socio economic potentials over time. Lakes are often subjected to gradual shrinkage or accumulation of mineral and organic sediments resulting from the combined influences of anthropogenic activities and climate change. Several studies have consistently pointed out the vulnerability of these important water resources to influences of land uses and climate change. Climate conditions and catchment land uses are among the major determining factors of lakes sedimentation [2]. It was also observed that lake Quinghai (China) have experienced significant shrinkage in its water level and surface area at rates of 5.28 cm yr^{-1} and $4.38 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ between 1959 and 2010, owing to trends of warming climate and anthropogenic influences [3].

Excessive sediment loading is a significant, widespread and pervasive form of aquatic pollution and remains a major form of anthropogenic disturbance of aquatic systems in both tropical and temperate regions [4-8]. Furthermore, re-emphasized that aquatic pollution by sediment loading poses considerable

negative impacts on biological diversity, ecological functioning and productivity of the affected water bodies [9]. Besides the impact of excessive sediment loading on basin morphology of natural lake systems, it is capable of affecting the water supply, fisheries and tourism of potentials of affected lakes and reservoirs as well as affecting their hydropower efficiency and cost of maintenance [4,10,11,9].

A common type of sediment load associated with floodplain lakes is Fluid Mud. This is a high-concentration aqueous suspension of fine sediment particles ($< 63 \mu\text{m}$) characterized by non-substantial settling properties [12]. Fluid Mud is characterized by visco plastic (pseudo plastic) properties, and constitutes predominantly clay ($>50\%$) and organic materials, with the clay fraction consisting of platy, cohesive minerals from the class of clays and micas rich in chlorite, illite, smectite, montmorillonite and kaolinite minerals [13]. The high accumulation of Fluid Mud in rivers, lakes, estuaries, and shelves constitutes a significant management problem by impeding navigation, reducing water quality and damaging equipment [12].

The morphometric parameters of lake basins are vital descriptors of the form and size of lake basins [14]. Therefore, temporal morphometric studies of lake basins are paramount to the understanding of lacustrine morphological structure, function and dynamics, as well as understanding the nature, magnitude and effects of changes in the lakes' hydro geo morphological characteristics. The size and form of lakes regulate such transport processes as sedimentation, internal loading and outflow of both water and sediments, which in turn regulate many abiotic state variables, such as concentrations of phosphorus, colour, water chemical variables and water clarity, which regulate primary production, which regulate secondary production [15].

Lake Mbemun also known as the Gyawana Lake [16] is a Fluvial Lake of much socio-cultural

and economic significance to the Bachama Chiefdom; A major and popular ethnic group in Adamawa State Northeastern Nigeria. The lake has been a significant small scale fishing spot for the indigenous Bachama people and other fishermen among the *Batta, Kwa, Jongjong, Jukun, Kabawa and Idoma* ethnic groups. On yearly basis, the fishermen engage in small scale fishing which mostly occurs between the months of February and April. However, speculations carry it that in recent times, the lake is losing this life-sustaining potential to rapid siltation and some forms of degradation associated with anthropogenic activities and climate change. The aforementioned cursory view, coupled with non-availability of the lake's morphometric information prompted the need for this baseline study on its hydro geomorphology. This also places much concern on the lake's viability for annual socio cultural fishing.

(Fig. 1). It is located between Latitudes 09°32'00"N and 09°33'30"N of the Equator and between Longitudes 11°48'30"E and 11°50'30"E of the Prime Meridian (Fig. 1 and Plate 1).

Geologically, the Lake area situated in the Yola arm of the Benue Rift, which is a section of the West African Rift system formed in the early cretaceous period [17]. Following the formation of the rift, the basement part of it was then overlain by two major sequential cretaceous sedimentary formations; The Bima Sandstones and the Yolde Sandstone sand Shales [18] on which is situated the lake.

Plate 1. Lake Mbemun

2. METHODS

2.1 The Study Area

Lake Mbemun is situated on the right bank floodplain of River Benue at Lamurde Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria

Fig. 1. The study area

Two major landforms characterize the relief of the area; The Lamurde hills in the northern part (198 m to 730 m.a.s.l) and the Benue valley flood plain (130m to 180m.a.s.l.) extending from the foot of the Lamurde hills to the right bank of river Benue .Cutting across the floodplain at different sections are numerous streams draining into River Benue and Lake Mbemun (Fig. 2).

The area falls within the Aw climatic zone of Koppen's climatic classification .It is marked by distinct wet and dry seasons, influenced by the movement of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ). The wet season lasts for about 5-6 months (May to October) with annual precipitation values 642 mm to1407 mm [19]. The wettest months are August and September while the driest months are February and March .Mean Annual Temperatures range from 27.3°C to 30.7°C, having April and May as the hottest months of the year and November and December as the coolest [19].The temperature regime of the Area is sometimes influenced by warm and cold breezes generated by air masses interplay between the land and River Benue adjacent to it.

The flood plain is characterized by alternate combination of Gleyic cambisol and vertisol classes of soils. These Soils are deep, poorly drained and medium textured ranging from loam,

sandy-loam, silty loam, and clay loam .Their colors range from dark brown (10 yrs 3/2) to very dark grey (10 yr 3/1) [20]. Characterized by moderate to high fertility, the soils support the cultivation of maize, rice, sugar cane, cowpea, sorghum, millet and vegetables as well as substantive razing.

The floral species of the area are categorized on life-form basis into scattered arboreal and aquatic vegetation forms [21]. The predominant boreal species include *Vitellaria paradoxa* (shear butter), *Pakia biglobosa* (locust bean), *Tamarindus indica* (tamarin), *Acacia albida*, *Zizipus.spp* and *Prosopis spp.* among others. The most dominating aquatic forms of the area are sub-grouped into Emerged Macro phytes, Floating Macro phytes, Sub merged Macrophytes and Phyto planktons (Alga. Spp).

The faunal life of the study area includes the Zooplanktons, (*Diaphana soma excisum*, *Diaphnia barbata*, *Ceriodophania cornuta*, *Moina micrura*, *Bog mimilongirostris*, *Tropodiato mus incognitus* and *Mesocyclops leukarti* etc.). *Insecta* (*Gyptochrinomos stififer*, and *Cloenfrauda lentum* etc.). Annelids (Earthworms).Nematode (*molusca* –*Cleapatra bulimiodes*, *Labeocoubie alestes*, *Synodritis.spp*, *Tilapia.spp.*, and *Hetarotis* [21].

Fig. 2. Relief of the study area

2.2 Hydrographic Survey and Bathymetric Mapping of the Lake

Hydrographic survey of the lake was conducted using Staff Sounding Method (SSM); A suitable method of depth sounding for shallow water bodies (<6.00 m deep) as described by [22] (Plate 2). Equipment used for the survey included a leveling staff, Garmin eTrex GPS and a boat. Depth soundings were conducted at 213 points within the lake. The depths (Z coordinates) and their corresponding X and Y coordinates in Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection system were obtained. The X and Y coordinates of points along the shoreline were also obtained for mapping.

The hydrographic data of the lake were tabulated in Microsoft Excel and Save in Text Tab Delimited Format (TTDF) in C-Drive folder. The data was then exported to Arc Map environment of Arc GIS 10.1. The data were added onto the Arc Map environment using the 'Add XY Data' tool in the tools menu. Finally, the lake's Bathymetric map was produced using the neighborhood interpolation tool of the spatial analyst tools. Considering the shallow state of the lake with a maximum depth less than 2.00m, the bathymetric map was produced at a depth interval of 0.25m (Fig. 3).

Plate 2. Determination of lake water depth at a sample point by Staff Sounding Method

Plate 3. Measurement of fluid mud depth at a sample point

Fig. 3. Bathymetric map of Lake Mbemun (March 2016)

Fig. 4. Fluid mud depth map of Lake Mbemun, (March 2016)

2.3 Survey of Fluid Mud Depth

The depths of the lake’s Fluid Mud Layer were obtained at 35 sampled points within the lake using the Sediment Depth Probe Method described by [23]. An improvised wooden probe (4m and 2½ inches thick) was used. At each point, the probe was vertically inserted through the soft fluid mud layer down to the fairly solid bottom with greater resistance. Pulling out the probe from the mud, the layer depth mark was easily observed and measured in meters with a measuring tape (Plate 3).

Using the same procedure for Bathymetric map preparation, a fluid mud depth map of the lake was prepared in the ArcGIS10.1 environment from the mud depths data obtained during the hydrographic survey. The fluid mud map was prepared at a depth interval of 0.30 m (Fig. 4).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Bathymetric map of the lake for March 2016 revealed the general shallow state and flat bottom nature of the lake basin (Fig. 3). It also showed the uniform and gentle slope condition of the basin, which is adequately suitable for accumulation and settling of sediments loaded

into the lake by in flowing streams and seasonal floods.

The morphometric properties of the lake as obtained from hydrographic survey bathymetric map analysis are provided on Table 1.

The lake’s Shoreline Elevation (h), which is the height of the lake’s shoreline above mean sea level (a. m. s. l) was found to be 136 m.a.s.l. During flood events, the lake is filled up with water beyond this level to cover the surrounding floodable areas. This process also enhances sediment focusing into the lake basin, thereby enhancing fluid mud accumulation. The Shoreline Length, being the farthest distance of the lake’s entire marginal line that marks the water and land boundary (perimeter of the lake) was measured at 10.58 km. Also characterized by a Maximum Length (Fetch) of 2.95 km, a Maximum width of 2.01 km and a Surface Area (A) of 3.65 km², the lake was considered adequately open to wind and waves impacts. With the lake’s fetch oriented in the direction of prevailing wind in the Upper Benue Valley, the lake was found to be frequently affected by waves, greater water mixing and sediment focusing from its eastern part. On basis shoreline Length and Surface Area coverage, the lake was

found to be the largest among the major fluviatile lakes of Adamawa State when compared to such large lakes as Geriyo, Gwakra, Pariya Ribadu and Pariya described by [25].

Lake Mbemun was also characterized by a Shoreline Development Index (SDI) of 1.5. This high value of SDI (>1.0) indicated that the lake was very crenulated and highly reflected the potentials for development of littoral plant communities as well as high potentials of biological productivity which include production [24].

The Maximum Depth of 1.21 m, Mean Depth of 0.81 m, Depth indicator of 1.48 and Relative Depth of 0.06% all signified the general shallow status of the lake. The shallow status of the lake notwithstanding, its water Volume of 2.99 mcm and 0.28 Index of Basin Permanence (a measure of permanent water holding performance) in dry season were found to be capable of supporting the biological productivity of vast fish species. This is in agreement with the findings of [16] in which 40 species of fish belonging to 16 families were identified in the lake. The most common fish species observed included *Lates niloticus*, *Gymnarchus niloticus*, *Heterobranchus bidosalis*, *Clarias anguilaris*, *Bagrus docmac*, *Bagrus bayad*, *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus*, *Clarotes laticeps*, *Malapterurus electricus*, *Hydrocynus foskalii*, *Mormyrops deliciosus*, *Mormyrus rome*, *Heterotis niloticus*, *Hemisyndontis membraneus*, *Citharinus citharus*,

Oreochromis niloticus, *Mugil cephalus*, *Lutjanus sp.*, *Hepsetus odoe*, *Physailia pellucida*, *Labeo coubie*, *Hyperopsis bebes occidentalis* and *Barbus occidentalis*.

Focused group discussions with the custodians of the lake and some long time fishermen in the area affirmed that fluid mud accumulation in the lake has been on increase over the years, owing to muddy sediment inputs by annual flooding of River Benue and excess irrigation water discharges from Savanna sugar cane plantation. Field observations confirmed that almost all the excess water ways (canals) from the sugar cane plantation are connected to streams which feed the lake with water and sediments (Fig. 2). Respondents of the focused group discussions further attributed the continual degradation of the lake to the persistent rain fed and irrigation farming practices in the area which contribute to sediment generation and loading into the lake.

The fluid mud map of the lake for March 2016 (Fig. 3) shows the spatial pattern of fluid mud depths of the lake. It revealed an uneven distribution of fluid mud accumulation with depths ranging from 0.44 m to 1.26 m. The map also revealed that the fluid mud layer was deeper around the eastern part of the lake and gradually decreased towards the west. This variation in mud accumulation pattern is strongly tied to the east-west pattern of water and sediment inflow into the lake. A mean fluid mud depth of 0.81 m

Table 1. Morphometric properties of the lake

S/No	Morphometric parameter	Symbol/Formulae	Dimension
1	Shoreline Elevation	h	136 m.a.s.l
2	Shoreline Length	SL	10.58 km
3	Surface Area	A	3.65 km ²
4	Maximum Length	L _{Max}	2.95 km
5	Maximum Width	W _{Max}	2.01 km
6	Maximum Depth	Z _{Max}	1.21 m
7	Mean Depth	Z _{Mean} =V/A	0.82 m
8	Depth Indicator	D _i = Z _{Max} / Z _{Mean}	1.48
9	Relative Depth	$z_r = \frac{50(z_m)\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{A_0}}$	0.06%
10	Shoreline Development Index	$SDI = \frac{SL}{2\sqrt{\pi A_0}}$	1.56
11	Volume	$V_{z_0-z_1} = \frac{1}{3}(A_{z_0} + A_{z_1} + \sqrt{A_{z_0} \times A_{z_1}})(z_0 - z_1)$	2.99 mcm
12	Index of Basin permanence	IBP = V/SL	0.28

Formulae adopted from [24]

was obtained which was an indication of very high mud accumulation capable of hindering the free movement of fishermen in the lake. Besides, this fluid mud characteristic of the lake and its shallow water status cannot support the staging of other water games such as swimming and canoe racing, which are associated with sociocultural fishing festivals.

4. CONCLUSION

Although the lake is endowed with reasonable fishery potentials, its fluid mud mean depths (0.81 m) and the sticky nature of the mud are capable of hindering smooth fishing activities. The only possible methods of fishing in the lake are those that may involve the use of canoes. Even though, the methods may not be suitable for the catch of large fish species.

Therefore, Lake Mbemunis considered not suitable for staging a socio-cultural fishing festival which involves the free movement of fishermen and application of various cultural fishing methods. Alternatively, dredging of the lake to a stable and shallow fluid mud level capable of supporting the free movement of fishermen is recommended.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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